

New medication to treat Focal Segmental Glomerulosclerosis

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Article History

Received: 02.07.2024

Accepted: 17.07.2024

Published: 24.07.2024

Abstract: -

Background: Focal segmental sclerosis (FSGS) is a common cause of nephrotic syndrome in adults and children that characterized by scar tissue formation in the glomeruli, which are responsible for blood filtration [1]. Focal segmental glomerulosclerosis (FSGS) is classified into two main categories:

1. Primary (Idiopathic) FSGS: This form of FSGS has no identifiable underlying cause. It occurs spontaneously and is thought to be related to genetic factors or immune system dysfunction.
2. Secondary FSGS: Secondary FSGS results from other conditions or factors that damage the glomeruli. These underlying causes can include obesity, infections, drug toxicity, kidney diseases (such as HIV-associated nephropathy), and certain systemic diseases [2].

In advanced stages, dialysis and kidney transplantation will be required. One of common treatments include immunosuppressive drugs, but they often do not provide a definitive cure and can have side effects due to immune system suppression [3].

Case presentation: In this article, we present a boy who was 13-year-old who sought medical attention due to kidneys pain and red-colored urine. The physician diagnosed it as focal segmental glomerulosclerosis, treated with antibiotics and immunosuppressants. Unfortunately, this approach proved ineffective, leading to the progression of the disease to severe stages, necessitating a kidney transplant. However, our medical team took a different approach. We combined traditional herbal remedies to halt the disease progression. Remarkably, this holistic treatment not only eliminated protein and blood in the urine but also completely reversed the FSGS.

Upon reviewing new test results and conducting clinical consultations, the previous treating physician, who had recommended the kidney transplant, concluded that neither the transplant nor their previously prescribed medications were necessary anymore.

Conclusion: Focal segmental glomerulosclerosis, which can occur due to infection and genetic factors, often has a limited response to standard treatments. This severe kidney disease, leading to renal inefficiency in many cases, may necessitate dialysis and kidney transplantation. In this particular case, at the request of patient's parents, we prescribed a combination of herbal remedies that were used for 45 days and caused remarkable results. Now, after 7 years of treatment, the patient's kidney functions effectively without any issues, with no presence of protein or blood in the urine.

Keywords: FSGS, Focal segmental sclerosis, glomerulosclerosis, herbal medicine, treatment of FSGS. Herbal medication for kidney, new treatment for glomerulosclerosis, treatment of excretion of protein and blood in the urine.

Cite this article:

Mohammadimoshganbar, D. A., Mostafavi, G., Hoorandghadim, A., (2024). New medication to treat Focal Segmental Glomerulosclerosis. *ISAR Journal of Medical and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2(7), 39-40.

Introduction:

In focal segmental glomerulosclerosis (FSGS), scar tissue forms in the glomeruli. Focal segmental glomerulosclerosis is a common cause of nephrotic syndrome in adults and children. Untreated patients with primary FSGS, presenting with nephrotic-range proteinuria (more than 5.3 grams per day) and hypoalbuminemia, typically progress towards end-stage kidney disease. In primary FSGS (idiopathic), no known cause for the disease has been identified. In secondary types, various factors such as infection, drug toxicity, underlying conditions like diabetes, HIV infection, and obesity can be involved.

Case presentation:

In 2017, a 13-year-old boy from Lebanon visited the hospital with complaints of flank pain and red-colored urine. The treating physician conducted several tests, including urine analysis, blood tests, and a CT scan. Here are the findings:

- **Urine Tests:**

Abundant protein and red blood cells (RBCs) were detected in multiple urine samples. The presence of WBCs and infection were also confirmed.

- **Blood Tests (CBC):**

Severe and continuous decreases were observed in the number of RBCs, hemoglobin (HB), and hematocrit (HCT).

- **CT Abdomen and Pelvis:**

The bladder wall was thickened, and there was interstitial fluid in the pelvis.

- **Abdominal Ultrasound:**

No gallstones were found.

- **Chest X-ray:**

Slightly contracted lungs were visible.

- **Kidney Biopsy and Pathology:**

The pathology report confirmed focal segmental glomerulosclerosis (FSGS).

After reviewing all the above results, the treating physician diagnosed the patient with focal segmental glomerulosclerosis and initiated antibiotic therapy. Immunosuppressive drugs were also prescribed. Despite taking prescribed medications, the patient's recovery did not progress. In 2017, the treating physicians

requested dialysis, and the patient underwent 2 sessions. Subsequently, the physicians recommended kidneys transplant.

Before the transplant, at the request of patient's parents, our team reviewed and noticed these facts:

1-All hospital tests

2-Patient's medical history from their parents.

3-Despite using immunosuppressive drugs, there was no improvement in the patient's condition.

4-Significant levels of white blood cells (WBC) were found in the urine.

We concluded that antibiotics resistant infection had caused the renal issue. Considering factors like the patient's weight, we prepared a combination of herbal medications. After 45 days of the patient taking our herbal medications, significant progress in the recovery process was observed. We believe that our combination of herbal medications, which is mixture of several herbal remedies, helps treat kidney infection and almost cleans the glomeruli from scars. We believe that our blend of herbal medications is effective in the early stages of the disease and before the kidneys fail to filter blood from Creatinine.

The hospital physicians responsible for the initial diagnosis and treatment noticed the patient's improvement. They observed the absence of protein and blood in the urine, as well as the absence of kidney pain. After a comprehensive evaluation, they determined that the patient had fully recovered, eliminating the need for dialysis or a kidney transplant. They also advised discontinuing prescribed medications, including antibiotics and immunosuppressive medications.

The patient continued taking our prescribed herbal medications for 45 days, and subsequent examinations in the following years confirmed a sustainable cure.

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